

Export Driven Growth of INDIA and Benefits from ASEAN: Opportunities for *Acche Din*

Dr. Himanshu Agarwal¹

1. Associate Professor, D. N. (PG) College, Meerut

ABSTRACT

India sees ASEAN as a key element to sustain growth and prosperity through agreements on trade-in services and investment as soon as possible. ASEAN, too, is looking towards India to play a chief role in gearing up the course of geo-politics and economic development of the region. India's economic stability, its image as a benign regional power and commitment to the reform process has created a positive image across Southeast Asia. Therefore, the convergence of interests between India and ASEAN on several fronts provides a firm foundation undergirding both current and future cooperation with regards to several fields including piracy, terrorism, drug trafficking, natural disaster relief, climate change and facing the rise of China. Thus, it is essential that every effort to address the current information and perception gaps and mind-sets that hinder the pace and scope for economic cooperation between ASEAN and India must be challenged.

With a 62 years long agro-socio-politico development system, India has achieved a lot. But, apart from such development points, gap between have and have not, population explosion, inequitable regional development, difference between rural and urban facilities, corruption, high inflation and the decreasing trust in the political system have also been the unwanted children of this welfare state: India.

A vital element in fructifying and sustaining the dynamics of this emerging economic relationship would be to develop trust and confidence in each other and operationalize the framework agreement. It is essential that the media and elites on both sides make every effort to address the current information and perception gaps and mind-sets that hinder the pace and scope for economic cooperation between ASEAN and India.

Key Words: Bilateral, Comparative Advantages, Substantial Growth, Economic Resurgence, Macroeconomic Fundamentals, Economic Integration.

INTRODUCTION

India and Southeast Asia have been very close to each other in terms of civilization, trade and cultural links date back thousands of years, may be prehistoric period. Ancient Indian classical epic, the *Ramayana*, travelled Southeast Asia with the Indian merchants as well as Hinduism and Buddhism across the sea by the 1st century AD, influencing the development of kingdoms and empires like *Srivijaya* in Sumatra and the *Majapahit* in Java, Bali and the Philippine archipelago. Indian influence is still visible today in Southeast Asian architecture, food, pop culture, language and religion. Not alone association in cultural issues, ASEAN is a good opportunity of trade for India. India, in the effort to boost its growth through export trade may tap this opportunity very easily.

Exhibit 1 Here

Table 1 Here

EXPORT LED GROWTH OF INDIA: CONCEPT

India, since independence and from the start of five year planning system has followed the policy of self sufficiency and further self reliance. There was a justified background behind this policy of self sufficiency. But, It is obvious that to prove to be a welfare state, we could not gather much concentration on the fronts such as positive balance of payment situations and inclusive economic development. Even today we have the regions like Orissa, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Eastern Uttar Pradesh where the rampant poverty prevails and we have other regions like Punjab, Haryana, Delhi, Gujarat and Goa which are affluent states.

A typical and widely accepted reaction of this type is expressed by Pandit Nehru, the first Prime Minister of Independent India in *Discovery of India* (1946, pp.403), while reporting on the deliberations in 1938 of the National Planning Committee which he chaired. To quote: "The objective for the country as a whole was the attainment, as far as possible, of national self-sufficiency. International trade was certainly not excluded but we were anxious to avoid being drawn into whirlpool of economic imperialism. We wanted to be neither victims of imperial power nor to develop such tendencies ourselves"

With a 62 years long agro-socio-politico development system, India has achieved a lot. But, apart from such development points, gap between have and have not, population explosion, inequitable regional development, difference between rural and urban facilities,

corruption, high inflation and the decreasing trust in the political system have also been the unwanted children of this welfare state: India.

These gaps have put a burning mark on the forehead of the country in the shape of insurgency and internal revolt of local people. This not only placed a heavy bearing on the developmental system but also eats away a handsome portion of budgetary arrangements.

For overcoming these constraints with some other fatal ones like unemployment, unequal regional development, education and child labour, infrastructural facilities, power, water and health amenities, government of India after a long struggle of 62 years and a worthwhile network proved to be nearly fail may be because of the policy structure or because of the vision of the policy makers or because of the rising population, diversification of national setup or because of the financial crunch in meeting out expenses for the removal of these basic constraints.

Thus, to move towards betterment of general life and high growth and development, an urgent dose of capital investment is required. Capital investment bases on the high national income. Therefore, to earn comfortable level of national income we have good opportunities at exports. The performance though creditable, it is felt that the India's export potential is not fully exploited. The gap between potential and performance can be attributed to lacunae in the delivery of promotional and extension services, lack of entrepreneurship and most on to the government's role in making, implementing and controlling of various laws and policy for export promotion. Here, the citings from a lecture of our worthy Prime Minister is worthwhile to quote, "A sustained vigorous increase in our exports is also essential for the continued viability of our balance of payments position and for improving our international credit worthiness. If our exports do not increase while our imports increase at an unsustainable rate, our balance of payments will come under pressure and there will be an adverse impact on our international credit worthiness, leading to increased uncertainty about the inflow of investible funds from abroad. We must not slip once again into a phase of development which lasted from the late 1950s until the mid 1990s when chronic shortage of foreign exchange had become a dominant constant on our development."

"Clearly, both our investment and export policies must be viewed in an integrated perspective. We must recognize that multinational corporation account for a major component of world trade in manufactures and also for the international flows of investible resources and transfer of technology. The Chinese and the East Asians seem to have grasped the significance

of these developments to the extent we have not been able to do thus far. Regrettably, we seem to be over obsessed with the fears about the return of the East India Company. I for one do not wish to assert that our opening up strategy is risk less. Increased competition can hurt the weak more so if no credible strategies are in place to enhance their efficiency and productivity. But I have sufficient faith in India's entrepreneurs to believe that, given a favourable supporting environment; they can stand on their feet and effectively meet the challenge of increased competition both at home and abroad." 1

Thus, it is attempted to study by making the case for accelerating the pace of active export orientation policies for achieving rapid and inclusive economic growth in India. Here, inclusive economic growth does mean the economic growth considering each and every region of the country. In this context, the study seeks to explore the positive instrumental role of export orientation of economic development of India by encashing over age old political, economic and cultural links with ASEAN.

RISE OF ASEAN

Established in August 1967, ASEAN (Association of South East Asian Nations) was the only first official organization that led economic integration in East Asia Region including the ASEAN Free Trade Agreement (AFTA), the ASEAN Framework Agreement on Services (AFAS) and the ASEAN Investment Area (AIA). Further, as an integral part of the ASEAN vision 2020, it aims to establish an ASEAN Security community, ASEAN Economic Community, and ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community by 2020. ASEAN through these allied communities hopes to establish a free single market and production unit of ASEAN countries by 2020 through a free flow goods, investment, services and a reduction in poverty and socio-economic disparity across the region.

All these initiatives were very low in the start but the 1997-98 crises boosted up the trends of regionalism automatically and tremendously. These indicatives include forming of regional trade agreements and measures to environmental, energy, cultural, educational, social, and institutional sectors. Thus, what has emerged is a framework for a virtual East Asian community.

1 Dr. Manmohan Singh, Prime Minister of India, Keynote Address at 55th All India Commerce Conference; "Global Business and Indian Economy"

ASEAN presently stands at juncture where it is looking to integrate nations in the region not just in matters of trade, but also at the bilateral level. There are significant complementarities that exist between countries in the region in terms of diverse comparative advantages and varied strategic and diplomatic advantages. Regional cooperation could help in exploiting the existing capacities in the region fully. To start with new fundamentals, ASEAN: Association of South East Asian Nations is a good opportunities to the country.

Ambassador of the Kingdom of Thailand to the Republic of India, Pisan Manawapat has said, "What the leaders of ASEAN and India are working toward go beyond "interaction". Both sides are aiming for "integration", as in the case of free trade arrangements between ASEAN and India. That is why both sides are putting their utmost effort to wrap up the negotiations in services and investment in time of the Summit and set the stage for commencing negotiations for the Regional comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP). The RCEP, which will also encompass China, Japan, South Korea, Australia, and New Zealand will create the largest single market in the world, surpassing the European Union. Altogether, this market of 4 billion people will account for over 28 per cent of global GDP.

We, not alone we, but ASEAN too, can extract good results out of ASEAN-India TIG (Trade in Goods) Agreement 13 August, 2009. The Signing of ASEAN – India Trade in Goods Agreement paves the way for the creation of one of the World's largest FTA Market of almost 1.8 billion people with a combined GDP of US \$ 2.8 Trillion. ASEAN- India TIG Agreement entered into force on 1 January, 2010.

ASEAN AND INDIA's EXPORT ATTENTION

The crisis of 1991 has established India in many terms. We have learnt a lot from such changes. It also let us to realize the need to change the inward-looking growth model that had been followed by India since the time of its independence, due to its inappropriateness in the post cold war era and an age of globalisation. Thus, a handful of reforms to restructure, deregulate and liberalize Indian economy have been pumped up. Further, economic orientation has been initiated to improve economic relations of India with other countries.

With substantial growth in the last decade, India has emerged as one of the largest economies not just in Asia, but the entire world. With the third largest GDP and a growth rate of 7-8 per cent, India is poised to emerge as a large economic power in the years to come. With a rising middle class and an economy on an upward trajectory, India has large economic

potential and provides ample opportunities its economic resurgence. ASEAN has certainly taken note of this fact and is aware that it is in its best interest to include India in a regional framework and thereby, capitalize on its emerging strength. One of the objectives of the Framework Agreement on Comprehensive Economic Cooperation signed between ASEAN and India is to “facilitate the more effective economic integration of the new ASEAN member states and the bridging of development gap among the parties.” There is growing awareness that regional disparities need to be addressed and cooperation increased, to broaden the range of countries that derive benefits from growth in the region.

The increasing relevance of India in the East Asian framework has contributed to its rising integration with ASEAN. Though there has been turbulence in their relations in the past, it is evident that the importance of integrating in today’s interconnected globalizing world has been recognized by countries in East Asia. With ASEAN as the established hub and the framework of regionalism in place in the region, it has been realized that it is prudent to include India and allow it to participate for increased benefits and growth.

Apart from merchandise trade, there has also been growing trade in commercial services. The services sector has been rapidly expanding in India with its growth in IT and Business Process Outsourcing services along with its rise in other East Asian economies. There has consequently been enhanced integration in their trade, especially due to improvement in technologies and increasing globalization. The combination of a large supply of top-notch, low-cost labour, high-quality software processes, and the scale to handle all types of work, has allowed the Indian software industry to excel in the world market.

Studies by Goldman Sachs suggest that “India has the potential to show the fastest growth over the next thirty and fifty years.” With the growing economic integration of the Indian economy, its growth effects are bound to spill over to other countries as well.

Economic Snapshot of India

Table 2 Here

Table 3 Here

Figure 1 Here

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in India expanded 5.30 percent in the third quarter of 2012 over the same quarter of the previous year. GDP Annual Growth Rate in India is reported by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. Historically, from 1951 until 2012, India GDP Annual Growth Rate averaged 5.9 Percent reaching an all time high of

10.2 Percent in December of 1988 and a record low of -5.2 Percent in December of 1979. In India, the annual growth rate in GDP at factor cost measures the change in the value of the goods and services produced in India, without counting government's involvement. Simply, the GDP value excludes indirect taxes (VAT) paid to the government and includes the original value of products without accounting for government subsidies. This page includes a chart with historical data for India GDP Annual Growth Rate.

In FY2011-12 and FY2012-13, GDP growth is forecast to reach around 7-7.5 percent, a significant slowdown from the 9-10 percent growth in the run-up to the global financial crisis, and the v-shaped recovery from it in FY2009-10 and FY2010-11. The slowdown is caused by structural problems, tighter macroeconomic policies, slow growth in the core OECD countries, and a base effect: growth in FY2010-11 was buoyed by the strong rebound in agriculture, while agricultural growth is expected to revert to trend (2.5 percent) in FY2011-12. Fiscal consolidation and higher interest rates are also likely to have a dampening effect on aggregate demand. The successive interest rate hikes by the RBI and recent decline in inflation have brought the real policy interest rate (nominal policy rate minus WPI y-o-y inflation) into positive territory for the first time since Q2 FY2009-10. This impacts in particular some long-term investments and demand for housing and consumer durables. Domestic interest rates could have a stronger effect on domestic investment than they hitherto had, because of the lower availability of external loans in the more uncertain international environment.

Shared Interests

While India's total trade volume with ASEAN is not as large as China's, its growth trajectory is equally remarkable. According to ASEAN statistics, total trade mushroomed from 2.9 billion in 1993 to 47.5 billion in 2008, and while in 2009 (as broadcast in July 2010) is 37.62 billion while India's share of total ASEAN trade quadrupled from just 0.7% in 1993 to 2.8% in 2008, and 2.5 % in 2009 (as broadcast in July 2010) making it ASEAN's seventh biggest trade partner. The 7th ASEAN India Summit in Cha-ain-Hua Hin, Thailand on 24 Oct, 2009 agreed to revise the bilateral trade target to US\$ 70 billion to be achieved in the next two years, noting that the initial target of US \$ 50 billion set in 2007 may soon be surpassed.

Meanwhile, ASEAN accounts for 10% of India's global trade and is India's fourth largest trading partner after the European Union (EU), the United States (U.S.), and China. Both ASEAN and India have a strong interest in intensifying this cooperation in the long run, albeit

for different reasons. In addition to the common goal of maximizing overall economic gain, India sees economic engagement with ASEAN as a way to develop its poorer northeastern states, while ASEAN views India's trade with Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam (or CLMV) as an opportunity to help these newer, less-developed members of the organization catch up and further intra-ASEAN trade and unity. Initially, these sub-regional initiatives with the CLMV countries (Cambodia Laos, Myanmar, and Vietnam) were perceived as a sign of India's failure in engaging effectively at the multilateral level with the ASEAN region. However, the ASEAN, has of late, appreciated India's sub-regional initiatives as part of a mutual strategy of diversifying India-ASEAN cooperation, given the greater urgency of developing the CLMV countries and their integration within ASEAN.

Volume of Trade and investment flows between ASEAN and India remained relatively low compared with other dialogue partners of ASEAN. Between 1993 and 2003, ASEAN-India bilateral trade grew at an annual rate of 11.2 per cent from US\$ 2.9 billion in 1993 to US\$ 12.1 billion in 2003. In 2011, the total trade between ASEAN and India was US\$ 68.4 billion, a growth of 23.4 Per cent from US\$ 55.4 Billion in 201. This accounted for 2.9 per cent of the total ASEAN trade in 2011. At the 8th ASEAN-India Summit in October 2010, the leaders reaffirmed their commitment to achieve bilateral trade target of US \$70billion by 2012. At the 10th ASEAN –India Summit in November 2012, the leaders set the target of US\$ 100 billion by 2015 for ASEAN-India trade. Acknowledging this trend and recognizing the economic potential of closer linkages, both sides recognized the opportunities for deepening trade and investments, and agreed to negotiate a framework agreement to pave the way for the establishment of an ASEAN- India Free Trade Area (FTA), which includes FTA in goods, services and investment.

ASEAN and India are currently negotiating the ASEAN-India Trade in Services and Investment Agreements. During the 10th ASEAN-India Summit in November, 2012, the ASEAN-India Leaders tasked their economic ministers to step up their efforts and flexibility to conclude the ASEAN-India Trade in Services and Investment Agreement at the earliest.

ASEAN and India are also working on enhancing private sector engagement, including the re-activation of the ASEAN-India Business Summit (AIBS) and an ASEAN- India Business Fair (AIBF) held in New Delhi on 2-6 March 2011. The events were part of the efforts to stimulate trade and business-to-business interaction. The 14th ASEAN Transport Ministers (ATM) Meeting on 6 November 2008 in Makati, Metro Manila, Philippines adopted

the ASEAN-India Aviation Cooperation Framework, which will lay the foundation for closer aviation cooperation between ASEAN and India.

Further on Connectivity, the 10th ASEAN-India Summit welcomed the establishment of India's Inter Ministerial Group on Connectivity and encouraged regular exchanges between the Group and the ASEAN Connectivity Coordinating Committee (ACCC) to explore concrete ways and means to support the MPAC, in particular in areas where India has strong expertise and interest.

Significant developments can also be seen in the cooperation in the agriculture and forestry sector as ASEAN and India Ministerial Meeting on Agriculture and Forestry on 8 October 2011 in Jakarta, Indonesia. The Ministers adopted the Medium Term Plan of Action for ASEAN-India Cooperation in Agriculture (2011-2015) with the view to promoting and intensifying cooperation in the agriculture and forestry sector between ASEAN and India, in order to meet the challenges of food security, to exchange information and technology, to cooperate on research and development projects, to encourage agriculture and forestry-related industries, and to strengthen human resources development.

With the ongoing restructuring of economic activities, physical connectivity is essential for the economic and financial integration of India and ASEAN. People-to-people connectivity via media and other forms of communication can help community groups, academic institutions and arts and cultural institutions, also cooperation in the areas of physical, digital, financial and media connectivity throws open huge opportunities for businesses in India and ASEAN.

While the attention is often on the economics of the relationship, ASEAN and India have much to gain from cooperation beyond this area. Security-wise, India's Shared maritime borders with Indonesia and Thailand, and long land border with Myanmar, means that India and ASEAN share joint concerns about and interests in counter-terrorism, anti-piracy, counter-narcotics, and sea lane protection. In the sea, the primary shared security interest is protecting the Strait of Malacca, which connects the South China Sea to the Indian Ocean and is one of the world's busiest sea routers, carrying goods vital to the economic viability and energy security of India and ASEAN. Insulating the sea lanes from piracy and crime is thus a key concern for both sides. And while incidences of piracy have fallen significantly over the last few years, Singapore's recent warning of a possible terrorist attack on oil tankers, suggests that the Strait will continue to be a security concern.

Therefore, the convergence of interests between India and ASEAN on several fronts provides a firm foundation undergirding both current and future cooperation. In addition to being strong economies and attractive markets, both share similar concerns and interests with regard to several fields including piracy, terrorism, drug-trafficking natural disaster relief, climate change and facing the rise of china.

Here, as has been discussed earlier, we have to shift over the export-led-growth model rather than age old self sufficiency model. These statements of the researcher do not contradict the basic vision of the policy makers and the pillars of the Indian economy, but, the locus of the problems of India has shifted and it can only be riddled out through the change in the vision and through setting of the effective strategy of future growth and development. Otherwise, we will fall weak and tender to the emerging socio-economic challenges from inside and outside.

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

The existing volume of trade between India and ASEAN has remained low despite the combined size of the two economies. Notwithstanding India's sustained economic growth, hovering around 7-8 per cent, India's share in ASEAN's total global trade has remained only 1 per cent. Negotiations on the ASEAN-India FTA in Goods have dragged on for the last three years over several issues and despite large-scale economic cooperation; the two-way FDI has remained marginal. India's policy of sectoral capping of FDI has further restricted the flow of ASEAN FDI into India. Economic cooperation is further complicated by the different levels of economic growth and development of the various ASEAN economies. This problem has been very much evident while negotiating the FTA in goods. India's bureaucratic entanglement has also acted as a major disappointment for ASEAN investment in India.

Even with these boosts, AIFTA in its current form only provides for the elimination of tariffs on 80% of items, with about 10% deemed 'sensitive' and classified under a reduced tariff track. The remaining 489 items are on the 'negative list' and not subject to any tariff cuts. Negotiations were also delayed by some ASEAN countries. For instance, Indonesia, the world's largest palm oil producer, raised a last minute demand for tariff reduction on crude and refined palm oil just as the deal was about to sealed, before later revising its offer.

India and ASEAN have both faced similar outbursts of discontent before as they pursued, or thought of pursuing, trade liberalization with countries such as china, and will

likely continue to do so in the future. In order to overcome fierce protectionist sentiment, leaders from both sides must display combination of vision, determination, and deftness. This will be particularly important as ASEAN and Indian pursue future agreements in the field of services and investments (the present agreement covers only trade in merchandise).

On the positive side, the nature and dynamics of India-ASEAN cooperation reflect both the cementing and diversification of regional operation, with the main objectives of greater integration and attainment of common objectives as spelt out under the plan of Action to Implement the ASEAN-India Partnership for peace, progress and shared prosperity. Over the years, ASEAN countries have shows their willingness to further engage India on the issues of bilateral, regional and international importance, thereby, creating more geo-strategic space for India to maneuver and rebuild the old historical, cultural, political and economic ties.

Arguably the greatest challenge to ASEAN – Indian relations, particularly in the economic realm, has been and will continue to protectionism. Hence, both ASEAN and Indian leaders must continue to resist protectionism in the future if they hope to deepen bilateral economic cooperation.

Table 4 Here

India's other sub-regional initiative with ASEAN-the Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC), which covers India, Thailand, Myanmar, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Nepal and Sri Lanka and was established in 1997, Also needs renovation. BIMSTEC certainly has band its fair share of successes. Despite meeting delays and implementation drags, priority areas of cooperation have broadened from six in 1997 to thirteen in 2006 and fourteen in 2009, while the grouping has signed agreements to set up an energy centre in India to promote grade interconnection in March 2010 and cooperate in combating international terrorism, transnational crime and illicit drug trafficking in 2009. But other measures have not been realized, including a free trade pact despite the fact that a framework agreement was inked in 2004.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The robust cultural and civilization between ASEAN and India in the past and the common interest that both parties share today means that there is significant potential for the development of a strong partnership for tomorrow. But an agenda for a future partnership is not forged by common interest alone. It will require bold decisions, innovative policies, and smart

politics on the of ASEAN and Indian leaders in order to both get past potential obstacles as well as push through initiatives that provide opportunities for enhancing the relationship. Only then can both parties get to a strong ASEAN – Indian partnership for the 21st century, and outcome that is beneficial not only to India and Southeast Asia, but the wider Asia-Pacific region as well.

With the ASEAN-India FTA in the offing, this partnership only stands to be further strengthened. There is a clear sense that ASEAN intends to integrate the East Asian region into one consolidated regional bloc and it is certain of the importance of having India as a part of it.

ASEAN sees India as an emerging power in Asia and is keen to develop relations it it that would be beneficial to countries within ASEAN and to the region as a whole. It realizes that India possesses large strategic capabilities and can be a strong stabilizing force in the region. Economically, India, with its burgeoning middle class, can be a significant market for ASEAN manufactures and consequently, and important and consequently, and important source of welfare for the region. There is a lot that ASEAN can gain from India's development in its service sector and it looks to develop wide ranging economic partnerships with her.

India understands that the ASEAN grouping consists of countries which have achieved significant development in the past 20 years. It is in its interest to establish beneficial linkages with the countries to benefit from their past experience and current standing. ASEAN's strategic location makes its stability crucial for India's energy and economic security, and it looks to develop its influence in the region by forging vital ties with ASEAN.

The ASEAN-India partnership holds ample potential for a successful future. As things stand, it is evident that both India and ASEAN are keen to establish a strong relationship with a long-term emphasis on greater cooperation and integration, apart from the strengthening of economic and strategic ties. While there are definite challenges to be addressed before achieving a consolidated East Asian Community, it is evident that conscious efforts are being made on both the sides in developing synergies for the shared prosperity and mutual benefit of India, ASEAN and the Asian region at large.

Economic Think Tank NCAER points out in this reference that India would witness a sustained growth of above 8 percent per year in the period between 2007-08 to 2011-12 backed by the positive effects of FDI and infrastructure development on productivity of various sectors. This requires the country to maintain an annual average growth rate of 8% per annum

as envisaged in India's 10th Five Year Plan (2007-11)²⁶. As India's vision of becoming a developed nation by 2020 continues to be translated into domestic reform initiatives and leads to its further integration with the world economy, the opportunities for ASEAN and other economic partners for mutually beneficial economic cooperation are likely to multiply. ASEAN is aware of the need to further diversify its engines of growth from the traditional growth engines of the US, Japan and more recently, China, to India as well. Diversification of growth engines and greater integration among the members are imperative if the region is to reduce its susceptibility to boom and bust cycles that it has faced since the mid 1990s.

The range of existing complementarities between ASEAN and India are substantial and still are not fully exploited. The groundwork for a significant expansion and intensification of economic ties is now in place with the establishment of the Frameworks Agreement for establishing a FTA. If India is permitted to be an observer of various technical committees is ASEAN that would facilitate the negotiations for an ASEAN-India FTA. It is therefore urged that both sides should urgently consider effective steps in the direction.

The two sides are also drawing up a roadmap called "Vision 2020" which is adopted at the Third ASEAN-India Summit in Laos in 2004. They have also agreed to undertake common efforts to help fight international terrorism and transnational crime, particularly the trafficking of drugs, weapons and humans. Steps should be taken to turn the current ASEAN plus Three (China, Japan and Korea) grouping to ASEAN plus Four by including India. This would also be an important step in moving towards the operationalization of the bolder vision of establishing a larger Asian Economic Community.

A vital element in fructifying and sustaining the dynamics of this emerging economic relationship would be to develop trust and confidence in each other and operationalize the framework agreement. It is essential that the media and elites on both sides make every effort to address the current information and perception gaps and mind-sets that hinder the pace and scope for economic cooperation between ASEAN and India. The significant complementarities that exist between ASEAN and India can only be realized if and when these ideological and informational blinders are lifted.

REFERENCES

1. Albar, Syed Hamid (2002). ASEAN-India Partnership: Opportunities and Challenges. India-ASEAN Partnership in an Era of Globalization. New Delhi: Research and Information System for the Non-Aligned and Other Developing Countries.
2. Anand, Mohit (2008). India-ASEAN FTA: Implications for India. Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies, No. 2664, 28 August 2008 [online] available: http://www.ipcs.org/southeastasia_publications2.jsp?action=showView&kValue=2680&country=1016&status=article&mod=a
3. Anand, Mohit (2008). India's Economic Competitiveness in ASEAN: A Comparison with China. Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies, No. 2692, 22 September 2008.[online] available:http://www.ipcs.org/southeastasia_publications2.jsp?action=showView&kValue=2708&country=1016&status=article&mod=a
4. Asher, Mukul G. and Sen, Rahul (2005). India-East Asia Integration: A Win-Win for Asia. Research and Information Systems for the Non-Aligned and Other Developing Countries RIS Discussion Paper, No. 91.
5. Asher, Mukul G. (2007). India's Rising Role in Asia. Research and Information Systems for the Non-Aligned and Other Developing Countries RIS Discussion Paper No. 121.
6. Ayoob, Mohammad (1990). India and Southeast Asia: Indian Perceptions and Policies. London: Routledge.
7. Banerjee, Dipankar (1996). Myanmar and Indian Security Concerns. Strategic Analysis vol. 19, pp. 691-705.
8. Christophe, Jaffrelot (2003). India's Look East Policy: An Asianist Strategy in Perspective. India Review, Vol. 2(2).
9. Devare, S. (2006). India & Southeast Asia: Towards Security Convergence, Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, Singapore. Developing Countries RIS Discussion Paper, No. 73.
10. Framework Agreement on Comprehensive Economic Cooperation between the Republic of India and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations. [online] available: ASEAN Official Website, <http://www.aseansec.org/15278.htm>, accessed on 16 November 2007
11. Gordon Sandy and Henningham Stephen (eds.) (1995) India Looks East: An Emerging Power and its Asia-Pacific Neighbors, (Canberra Papers on Strategy and Defense,

- no.111) Canberra, Australia, Strategic and Defence Studies Centre, Australian National University
12. Grare, Frederic and Mattoo, Amitabh (eds.) (2001) *India and ASEAN: The Politics of India's Look East Policy*, New Delhi, Manohar Publishers & Distributors
 13. Hong, Zhao (2006). India's Changing Relations with ASEAN: From China's Perspective. East Asian Institute Working Paper No. 133.
 14. Iyengar, Partha (2006). India's ICT Industry: Increasing in Global Visibility and Relevance, 18 April 2006. [Online] available: Gartner Research Website. http://www.gartner.com/DisplayDocument?doc_cd=138416 (accessed on 19 November 2007).
 15. Jaffrelot, Christopher (2003). India's Look East Policy: An Asianist Strategy in Perspective. *India Review*, vol. 2, no. 2, Pp. 35-68.
 16. Kaul, Man Mohini (2002). Time for a Great Leap Eastwards. *The Indian Express*, 20 November 2002. [Online] available: <http://www.mea.gov.in/opinion/2002/11/20o03.htm> (accessed on 17 November 2007).
 17. Kawai, Masahiro (2005). East Asian Economic Regionalism: Progress and Challenges. *Journal of Asian Economics*, Vol.16 (1). Pp. 29-55.
 18. Kawai, Masahiro and Wignaraja, Ganeshan (2007). ASEAN+3 or ASEAN+6: Which Way Forward. Asian Development Bank Institute ADBI Discussion Paper No. 77.
 19. Kumar, Nagesh (2005). Towards a Broader Asian Community: Agenda for the East Asia Summit. Research and Information Systems for the Non- Aligned and Other Developing Countries RIS Discussion Paper, No. 100.
 20. Kumar, Nagesh, Sen, Rahul and Asher, Mukul (eds.) (2006) *India-ASEAN Economic Relations: Meeting the Challenges of Globalization*, Singapore, Institute of Southeast Asian Studies
 21. Kuruvilla, Benny (2006). Services Industry Drives India GATS Negotiations. [online] available: Focus on the Global South Website, 30 June 2006, <http://www.focusweb.org/services-industry-drivesindia-gats-negotiations.html>, accessed on 16 November 2007
 22. Muni, S.D. (2006). East Asia Summit and India. Institute of South Asian Studies Working Paper, No. 13.
 23. Nathan, K.S. (ed.) (2000). *India and ASEAN: The Growing Partnership for the 21st Century*, Kuala Lumpur, Institute of Diplomacy and Foreign Relations.

24. Parthasarathy, G. (2002). The Gains of Looking East. *The Pioneer*. 21 November 2002. [Online] available: <http://www.mea.gov.in/opinion/2002/11/21o03.htm> (accessed on 17 November 2007).
25. Prasad, Malla V.S.V. (2006). Political and Security Cooperation between India and ASEAN. In Kumar, Sen and Asher, Mukul (eds.), *India-ASEAN Economic Relations: Meeting the Challenges of Globalization*. Singapore: Institute of Southeast Asian Countries.
26. Rajamohan, C. (1995). India's Role in South East Asia, in Michael W. Everett and Mary A. Somerville (eds.) *Multilateral Activities in South East Asia: Pacific Symposium*, Washington, DC, National Defense University Press, Pp. 87-110.
27. Sen, Rahul (2006). New Regionalism in Asia: A Comparative Analysis of Emerging Regional and Bilateral Trading Agreements Involving ASEAN, China and India. *Journal of World Trade*, Vol. 40, No. 4, Pp. 553-596.
Sen, Rahul, Asher, Mukul G and Rajan, Rakishen S. (2004). *ASEAN-India Economic Relations: Current Status and Future Prospects*. Research and Information Systems for the Non-Aligned and Other.
28. Singh, Jaspreet. (2003). Country Analysis: India. [online] available : American University Website, 5 December 2003, <http://www.american.edu/initeb/js5518a/Countryanalysis-india.html>, accessed on 16 November 2007
29. Singh, Swatan (2001). China Factor in India's Ties with Southeast Asia. In Frédéric Grare and Amitabh Mattoo (ed.), *India and ASEAN: the politics of India's look east policy*, (New Delhi: Manohar, (2001), p. 199.
30. Sridharan, Kripa (1996) *The ASEAN Region in India's Foreign Policy*, Brookfield, VT, Dartmouth Publishing Co.
31. Sridharan, Kripa (1996). *India and ASEAN: The Long Road to Dialogue*, Round Table no.340, Pp. 465-477.
32. Sundararaman, Shankari (2002). India and ASEAN. *The Hindu*, 19 November 2002. [Online] available: <http://www.mea.gov.in/opinion/2002/11/19o02.htm> (accessed on 17 November 2007).
33. Vajpayee, A.B. (2002). India's Perspectives on ASEAN and the Asia Pacific Region, 9 April 2002. [online] available: India's Ministry of External Affairs Website, <http://www.mea.gov.in/sshome.htm> (accessed on 17 November 2007).

All Data in this section are latest as per the availability.

Exhibit 1: Southeast Asia Map

Table 1: Timeline of Important ASEAN-Indian Economic Events

Year	Event/Agreement
1950s	Close Relationship with ASEAN countries by supporting the Indonesian struggle for independence.
Early 1990s	India encountered balance of payment crisis. India thus, adopted policy of liberalization and greater linkages with the global economy. India launched Look East Policy under then PM Narasimha Rao.
1992	Sectoral Dialogue Partnership of ASEAN
1995	Full Dialogue Partnership of ASEAN
1996	Membership in ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF)
1997	Establishment of Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi – Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC-Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Thailand Economic Cooperation).
2002	First India-ASEAN Summit and India – ASEAN Business Summit
2003	Framework Agreement of Comprehensive Economic Cooperation Second India-ASEAN Summit India Signs Treaty of Amity and Cooperation.
2004	ASEAN-India Partnership for Peace, Progress and shared Prosperity. Third India-ASEAN Summit.
2005	India Becomes member of East Asian Summit.
2007	Fifth India-ASEAN Summit and Second East Asian Summit.
2009	Signing of the ASEAN-India Free Trade Agreement (AIFTA) which had a combined market of almost 1.8 billion people and a combined GDP of US \$ 2.75 trillion.
2010	A free-trade agreement between China and the 10 members of the Association of Southeast Asia Nations (ASEAN) came into effect.
2011	AIFTA became fully operational. An AIEPG has been set up to draft a new ASEAN-India Vision 2020.
2012	ASEAN- India Think Tank Round Table on Economic Dynamics, New Delhi ASEAN Economic Ministers + India Consultations & Related Meetings, Cambodia. India ASEAN Agri Expo, New Delhi. 2 nd India-ASEAN Business Fair and Business Conclave, New Delhi.

Compiled by the Author himself from various resources

Table 2: Annual Growth in Gross Domestic Product (At 2004-05 prices in Rs. Crore)

Industry	2009-10	2010-11 QE	2011-12 RE	% change	
				10-11	11-12
1. Agriculture, forestry and fishing	662,509	709,103	728,667	7.0	2.8
2. Mining and Quarrying	104,225	109,421	108,469	5.0	-0.9
3. Manufacturing	719,728	774,162	793,468	7.6	2.5
4. Electricity, Gas and Water Supply	88,266	90,944	98,105	3.0	7.9
5. Construction	355,717	384,199	404,617	8.0	5.3
6. Trade, Hotel, Transport, and Communication	1197,213	1,330,455	1,462,772	11.1	9.9
7. Financing, Insurance, real estate and business services	769,883	849,995	931,714	10.4	9.6
8. Community, Social and Personal Services	610,096	637,675	674,703	4.5	5.8
Total	4507637	4885954	5,202,514	8.4	6.5

Source: Central Statistics Office (CSO), Government of India.

Table 3: Annual Growth in Gross Domestic Product (At Current prices in Rs. Crore)

Industry	2009-10	2010-11 QE	2011-12 RE	% change	
				10-11	11-12
1. Agriculture, forestry and fishing	1079365	1269888	1417366	17.7	11.6
2. Mining and Quarrying	157400	191207	223922	21.5	17.1
3. Manufacturing	907032	1040345	1143510	14.7	9.9
4. Electricity, Gas and Water Supply	112522	124038	136002	10.2	9.6
5. Construction	502190	585265	670735	16.5	14.6
6. Trade, Hotel, Transport, and Communication	1485476	1755531	2072376	18.2	18.0
7. Financing, Insurance, real estate and business services	962186	1170522	1395540	21.7	19.2
8. Community, Social and Personal Services	885314	1020616	1173202	15.3	15.0
Total	6091485	7157412	5,202,514	17.5	15.0

Source: Central Statistics Office (CSO), Government of India.

Figure 1: India GDP Annual Growth Rate (% change in GDP)

Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation

Exhibit 2: The 7th ASEAN India Summit in Cha-ain-Hua-Hin, Thailand

Source: Economic Times, 25 October, 2009.